

OSCAR

Career Coaching & Mentoring Program

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Definitions

Difference between Mentoring & Coaching

It is important to differentiate between Mentoring & Career Coaching for both mentees/mentors and coachees/Coaches.

Coaching is defined as “Partnering with clients in a thought-provoking and creative process that inspires them to maximise their personal and professional potential, which is particularly important in today’s uncertain and complex environment.” (International Coach Federation definition of coaching - <https://coachingfederation.org>))

Mentoring is defined as “a learning relationship, involving the sharing of skills, knowledge, and expertise between a mentor and mentee through developmental conversations, experience sharing, and role modeling. The relationship may cover a wide variety of contexts and is an inclusive two-way partnership for mutual learning that values differences.” (European Mentoring & Coaching Council - <https://www.emccglobal.org/>))

Within the coaching/mentoring relation, the coach/mentor is the instructor, expert or advisor. The coachee/mentee in turn is the learner, user, student or employee.

Implementation in OSCAR

Mentoring and career coaching are highly relevant within the OSCAR framework, as users may want to rely on the support from various mentors for their career and skills development. While not being a primary aim of OSCAR, we also include the option of receiving life coaching when this need would emerge while discussing the career progression and eventual career changes that need to be made.

Mentoring and coaching types

1. **Near-Peer Mentors (NPM).** This involves a mentoring relationship between individuals that are ‘closer in age, experience and rank (Eisen et al., 2014). The more “senior” mentor is somewhat more experienced and the primary goal of this mentoring is to ensure this experience-based

knowledge transfer. Because the mentor's experience was often acquired in relatively similar circumstances, this type of mentoring is well suited for a more continuous knowledge transfer between different cohorts.

2. **Peer-to-Peer (P2P)**. This involves mentoring that is conceptualised in diverse ways; Turban and Lee (2008) describe it as “an intense interpersonal exchange between a senior, experienced, and knowledgeable employee (i.e. the mentor) who provides advice, counsel, feedback, and support related to career and personal development for a less experienced employee”. For early career researchers (ECRs), this type of mentoring comes close to learning-by-doing whereby users actively implement newly acquired knowledge (through training) and share tips and tricks on how to overcome potential obstacles and/or share best practices that they experienced along the way.
3. **Career Coaches** As defined by Kamens, J (2015), career coaching helps individuals achieve their career goals. Professionals typically provide the coaching service, while they do not necessarily have to be experts in the user's skill set. However, they need to be trained in various career-coaching techniques so that they are fully equipped to effectively help users to (a) manage their present performance and (b) support the development of short, medium and long-term goals related to their career. Quality assurance of external coaches is crucial to build credibility and coaches need to be selected based on their accreditation, qualifications and a summary of services that they can offer the users.

Mentor and coach profiles

Within OSCAR, we will create a repository including profiles of mentors and coaches in which we highlight the specific skills and services they can offer along with their qualifications. Such database can then easily be used to (automatically) match users with the best suited mentors/coaches. Table 1 provides a sample career coach profile, summarizing the information that will be included in the repository. Building a rapport with the mentors/coaches online via eDoer is important so that users get a “feel” for their mentor/coach. The more information we can provide to the user on style and skills available, the better matching can be achieved between user and coach/mentor.

Personal Details	Academic Qualifications, Affiliations & Professional Training	Skills & Services Available	Years Experience (0-5 years)	Years Experience (5-10 years)	Years Experience (10 + years)
Name		CV Construction			x
Gender		Linked in Profiling		x	
Language		Interview Skills			x
Nationality		Career Planning			x
Picture		Career Change Strategies		x	
Why they got involved in Mentoring?		Relocation	x		
Why get involved in OSCAR?		External Roles		x	
Website		Working with ECR's	x		

Table 1: Sample of a career coach profile, including all information that will be stored in the repository of mentors and coaches.

Specialty Coaching

While discussing career progression and in particular when doubts would arise with regard to career changes, users may feel the need to request a more general coaching, focusing on life, relationship, family, fitness etc. While such specialised coaching does not fall within the current scope of OSCAR (also not being part of our mental health and wellbeing programme), it can often be required that a career coach works on non- career related topics from time to time. When more help is needed, they can

suggest more specialised support from other professionals. Similarly for career coaches, a repository of skills and competencies of such external professionals can help users to better identify the services that are on offer. However, this matching will not be automated at this stage nor will it be part of the standard procedure. At this stage, it is an optional service that we provide outside of the original project scope. At a later stage however, we can also integrate this structurally within the framework.

Procedural information

Using both Mentors & Coaches

Mentoring and coaching services may occur both independently and/or jointly, depending on the user's needs. For some users for instance, a joint effort may be required during which the mentor helps with some technical or publishing skills while, in parallel, the user may be preparing for an internal/external promotion or career change for which specific career coaching is needed.

Coaching Conversations

Whatever format is chosen to communicate (e.g. online, phone or face to face), four components are essential for good coaching to occur;

1. Conversation
2. Communication
3. Connection
4. Confidentiality.

They are essential to build trust, stimulate self-discovery, reflection and growth by the coachee/mentee.

A number of resources exist for coaching conversations and especially the Book "Opening the Door to Coaching Conversations" by Gross Cheliotas, L. and Reilly, M. (2012), highlights five key pillars that we incorporate in OSCAR (see table 2).

<p>Committed Listening</p>	<p>Committed listening (aka Active Listening) is about making a strong and intentional connection with the coachee/mentee by paying detailed attention to them. This is important as the mentor/coach notices not only what they say but also their emotional state, body language as well as their (life) story.</p>
<p>Paraphrasing</p>	<p>Paraphrasing is simply summarising what you - as the coach or mentor - heard from the mentee/coachee. This helps to ensure clarity, understanding and alignment between both parties.</p>
<p>Presuming Good</p>	<p>Coaching requires that the coach/mentor suspends their personal beliefs and any negative thoughts or comments that could influence the coachee/mentee. This allows them to remain objective and neutral and therefore capable of conveying their support for the coachee/mentee, even in challenging situations</p>
<p>Powerful Questions</p>	<p>Asking open-ended questions (questions which cannot be answered with a simple ‘yes’ or ‘no’) are designed to help the coachee/mentee clarify their thinking and their learning, even when related to ‘bad’ or ‘regrettable’ situations. Using context, tone and compassion in asking questions can really help as well in the coaching process.</p>
<p>Feeding Back</p>	<p>This skill is important because it enables the coachee/mentee to know themselves better, identify any blockages that are holding them back and help them make decisions about changes they would like to make, including being aware of the effect that those changes can have on themselves and others. The feedback needs to be clear, specific and delivered in a style that the coachee/mentee understands.</p>

Table 2: The five key pillars for coaching conversations (based on Cheliotis and Reilly, 2012)

Recruiting, Selecting & Training of Mentors & Coaches

It is crucial mentors and coaches are recruited through standardised procedures and selection criteria. In addition, we need to provide a clear job description and/or guidebook to help mentors/coaches understand what is expected of them.

Recruiting

The recruiting process and related selection criteria will need to be carefully assessed, standardized and fully transparent. All information needs to be clearly communicated so that candidates understand the process, timeframe and format for selection. Also, the identification of staff within the OSCAR Project will be key to the ongoing recruiting and selection of mentors and coaches. Some OSCAR Partners may need training on how to set up interview questions to validate the mentors/coaches competence.

Selection

The selection criteria for the mentors and coaches should include:

- Essential Skills & Experience
- Preferred Skills & Experience
- Ideal Skills & Experience

Depending on the specific type of mentor or coach, different selection criteria can be further defined. Table 3 provides an overview of specific profile types and the selection criteria based on which they will be recruited.

Type	Essential Skills & Experience	Preferred Skills & Experience	Ideal Skills & Experience
NPM	Completing PhD. In related area	Finished PhD in related area with 1-2 years PQE	Has mentored ECR's previously
P2P	Minimum of 4-5 years experience post qualification in academic or related area	Has published scientific research in related areas	Has successfully mentored ECR's in publishing
Coach	Has recognised active coaching qualifications or affiliations from an internationally recognised coaching organisation & 1-3 years' experience working with individuals in career coaching roles	Has 5 – 10 years experience in career coaching individuals in all aspects of career including assessment, management, development & change skills	Experienced in working with academic professionals in developing short, medium and long term strategies for internal and external roles as well as strategies for transitioning to roles outside of academia.

Table 3: Overview of the different skills and experience levels that will be identified during recruitment

Training

Once they are recruited, mentors/coaches will follow a standard online training program that focuses on the key models used within OSCARs training and mentoring framework. In addition, they will receive a tutorial in the form of a “simulated coaching session” so they fully understand how to use the different models. The training will be based on (a) CALP’s 5 Steps to Success Coaching Methodology, (b) the GROWTH model and (c) the BOOST feedback model.

At the end of the training program, learning outcomes will be assessed to ensure that coaches and mentors acquired the necessary skills to provide high quality support. Also, some FAQ or video tutorials for coaches/mentors who may experience something that they are unfamiliar with could be looked at to ensure coaches/mentors are given adequate and regular support. If mentors/coaches are not engaged,

then there is a risk of having too many users and not enough mentors. Therefore it is crucial to ensure that they feel part of the community. Ongoing training, networking and support systems should thus be part of our offer towards mentors and Coaches so that they are supported at all stages of their engagement with OSCAR.

How will a User choose a Coach / Mentor?

Initially, a questionnaire should be designed which will determine which “type” of human support the user prefers. Once this has been agreed on, further questions can be added or a free-text statement created to help map out the specific (or vague/general) area(s) that they need support with. For some however, answering questions may be too restrictive, the question they want to ask may not be listed in drop down fields or the issue they are facing is something they do not want to highlight in a database. Examples include, feeling bullied or abused or not knowing what to do in certain unplanned situations in work or home environments.

The Matching Process

Based on the recommendations by eDoer regarding learning outcomes, the selection can occur based on the mentee's needs. The mentee can also bypass the recommendations and choose a mentor/coach to work on a related or different area. Ideally, all matching should be facilitated through the system whereby, through correct alignment of questions, users can either choose a mentor/coach that best suits them or post a question to the community and engage with the mentee/coachee.

The matching process can thus occur from self-matching, system matching and community support. Table 4 gives a detailed description of these three processes. Different approaches will need further research and workflows will need to be created to suit.

Self-matching	mentee selects the mentor / coach based on their needs and mentor / coach profile
System Matching	based on questions being asked and a pool of mentors/coaches is Recommended
Community Support	This is where the users can post questions / look for support and other users, Mentors, Coaches and Contributors can answer

Table 4: Three matching process to link users with their mentor/coach

Duration & Frequency

Depending on the type of support required, two options are recommended:

1. Short Term Support:

- 16-week duration
- 1 Discovery/Introduction Session
- 5 Coaching / Mentoring sessions (45 to 60mins) scheduled every 3rd week

2. Long Term Support

- 26 – 52 week duration
- 1 Discovery/Introduction Session
- 12 Coaching / Mentoring sessions (45 to 60mins) scheduled every month

Capacity of the Mentor / Coach will need to be set so that no more than three mentees/coachees will be assigned at any one time. This is something that can be flagged in the system so users will get the chance to plan when they can get support from their preferred Mentor/Coach.

Quality Control during Mentoring / Coaching

During both short and long term sessions, it is important to ensure the standards agreed by OSCAR for both parties are assessed to ensure that no issues arise that could impact negatively on the project. If expectations are set upfront for the Mentor/Coach for a number of sessions with a Mentee/Coachee, then we should look to build a reporting system that demonstrates the number of mentoring/coaching

sessions that were agreed are happening. This will build trust with users when they can see the numbers of ECR's availing of mentoring/coaching and help to get more people engaged in both mental health and career coaching conversations.

References

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